

Role of Teachers in Effective Implementation of Teaching and Learning Processes at Secondary School Level of Education in Nigeria

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Abstract

This paper x-rays the Role of Teachers in effective Implementation of teaching and learning processes at secondary school level of education in Nigeria. Hence, there is need for quality teachers through which education industry can be effectively utilized for transforming Nigeria for the socioeconomic growth and national development. Teachers are the main determinants of quality in education, but if they are apathetic, uncommitted, lazy, unmotivated, immoral, anti-social, demoralized and unethical, the whole nation is doomed. It was discovered that, problems characterizing teacher education in Nigeria include lack of training and re-training. The paper concluded that, a teacher has a tremendous role to play in the realization of the National objectives based on the National policy on Education via Millennium Development Goals. To provide this important instrument for the socioeconomic and National development of the Giant of Africa which in turn will lead to the transformation of Nigeria. Recommendations were made, these include among others adequate funding of the sector at all levels.

Keywords: Secondary Education, Teaching and Learning

Introduction

Teaching as Profession is the bedrock of all other profession and therefore, it is the foundation of all profession on human sustainable development. A Teacher is a person who impart knowledge to his pupils, imparts good morals by showing good examples, teach discipline, encourage good habits, discourage bad ones both within and outside the class room which help the pupils not only in the school, but even their various communities, teaching is a profession that has prescribed educational programme (s) and objective (s) through which teachers acquire knowledge and skills needed for an effective, meaningful, successful service delivery. From time-to-time, teachers have to decide which techniques would be most suitable or appropriate for any prevailing circumstances in the classroom. Again, teaching is a multi-dimensional activity that is geared towards impacting knowledge and change in the existing behavior of a child through instruction (s). In the Art of teaching, there is no single method that can be described or considered as most suitable or not appropriate. What is best depends on the teacher, the ability of students to assimilate and comprehend the learning situation and the content of the lesson. Both selection and application of methodology depends on the teacher's ability to achieve the set objectives (Mahuta, 2009).

When the concept of "teaching" is mentioned, different people will have different conception of it. Some may completely mis construct what teaching is. It is therefore, imperative that prospective teachers should as a matter of their preparation for the task of teaching, be aware of the right conception of teaching. Whether we view teaching as an occupation or a profession, we must acknowledge the fact that teaching is both an art and science. As an art it can be practiced under skillful tutelage towards perfection, and as a science it can be learned. Teachers are the catalyst of the expected changes on the society. The National Policy on Education (UPE) lays emphasis on professional development of teachers as it recognizes "in-service as an integral part of continuing teacher education and shall also take care of all inadequacies". The teacher being tool for implementation of UBE need to be professionally develop, such that he can bring the desired changes in the society. This professional competence becomes essential because the validity of any educational system naturally is dependent upon the

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quality of the teaching and the availability of competence teachers. Giving credence to this statement Adesokan (2000) referred to the teacher as the spark and key man in the Drive to progress in the educational enterprise (Goshe, 2007)

From the afore-mentioned, one can evidently conclude that teaching is not just being able to stand in front of your pupils and speak the language they understand but the ability to use appropriate communicative techniques to facilitate and promote their understanding. In view of this, therefore, people should discard the wrong notion that everyone can teach. Having a university degree is not a sufficient qualification for one to teach. Teaching qualification is pre-requisite for dissemination of knowledge. The right of teachers in freedom of association, to collectively bargain and to undertake industrial actions are recognized in several labor international organization (ILO) recommendations and conventions. The low or meagre salary of teachers in Nigeria, the non-payment of salaries for prolonged periods of time in some Local Government Education Authorities, and the hiring of teachers on fixed-term contracts, create situation of low esteem, demoralization and even precariousness, all of which have negative impacts on the teachers' work as well as their dignity. This subsequently affects the general development of the youth and the nation at large. In recent years, the importance of education has been rediscovered; the World Conference on Education for All in Jomtiem in 1990 saw government leaders' efforts to make global commitments. The UN World Summit for development in Copenhagen, held on March 1995, stressed the need for a new deal for investment in education. In its Policy report "Strategies and Priorities" published in August 1996, the World Bank has emphasized the importance of investing in education. Any education authority or government that seriously wishes to improve education has to recognize the key role, which teachers play in the education process. One of the important measures that can be taken to improve the working condition of teachers. Quality education requires teachers whose high qualifications are socially recognized. In order to recruit qualified young people into the teaching profession and to teachers in teaching profession there is need to improve the working conditions of teachers in Nigeria. It is a fact that, the low salary scale for teachers coupled with the problems of lack of status of recognition by the members of the society and poor conditions of service are seriously affecting the teaching profession in Nigeria (Mahuta, 2009).

National Objectives

Abdul Malik (2007) posited that for us to focus on the attainment of the millennium development goals, the National Policy on Education (2014) outlined the five National objectives section 1 under the philosophy of Nigerian Education as follows:

1. A free and Democratic Society;
2. A just and egalitarian Society;
3. A united, strong and self-reliant nation;
4. A great dynamic economy;
5. A land of bright and full opportunities of all citizens

The above National objectives are expected to be fully disseminated to all teachers during training as they will be required to guide all students/pupils in their care to digest the objective to serve as their guiding principles when they conduct themselves any in Nigeria. Teachers would be models that should be seen by their Pupils to be practicing every aspect of the objectives within the society. The effort to attain the objectives will go a long way to prepare ground for the attainment of the Millennium Goals. There are various definition of teaching given by various scholars. Some widely accepted definitions of teaching include the following:

1. The act of practice of imparting to a learner knowledge, skills, values and norms that will be useful to the total development of the individual (Ekwueme, 2001)
2. Teaching is an art of imparting whole-heartedly useful knowledge in various forms and ways, formal or informal and by using all the communication media possible under proper guidance to enlighten the learner (Abdul Malik, 2007)
3. Teaching can be considered as any means by which an individual creates an understanding of a new knowledge on the part of the learner. This shows that this could be oral, practical, planned or unplanned, but it enables the learners to acquire values or skills which they had not known. It involves explaining, demonstrating, guiding and counseling by the teacher in order to effect a change in the learner (Abdul Malik, 2007)

Scope and Purpose of Secondary Education in Nigeria's Context

Secondary education is provided for children after primary education, that is, before tertiary education. It is aimed at developing a child better than the primary level, because it is obvious that primary education is insufficient for children to

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acquire literacy, numeracy, and communication skills (Ige, 2011; Yusuf, 2009). Such education is provided in secondary school, which can be owned by government (State or Federal), individuals or community. It is divided into two phases as follows:

Concept of Learning

Over the years, psychologists and educators realized that it is very difficult to define learning in a precise way. Some psychologists view learning as 'change' Behaviorist like B.F Skinner the 'father of behaviorism' argue that learning place when certain environmental conditions occur, apparently independent of any conscious human development. Thus, those who have adopted a behavioral view point describe learning as a 'relatively permanent process that results from practice and is reflected in changes in performance. Human learning basically is concerned with acquiring knowledge skills and attitude. We talk about learning how to read and write, how to drive a car, how to make a basket, sew dresses, operate a typewriter, memorize the line of a play play the piano or flute and how to decorate our homes. We learn about societies, about science and Technology and about values. All these acts are new performances which we acquire with reinforced practice. Learning is a fascinating interactive process involving the student (the learner) and the teacher within a learning environment (Mbakem & Ike, 2017)

The Beginning of Teaching in Nigeria

Teaching is one of the oldest and most important occupation in any society in the world. Teaching as an old craft, is as old as this world. Islam and Christianity are two dominant religions that to a great extent, influence all educational matters in Nigeria. Islam predated Christianity in Nigeria and Islam education has a long history in the country. The origin of formal teaching in Nigeria was intricately linked with the history of formal or western education. It should be noted that the discussion of western education in this country is directly connected to the missionary's activities. The first missionaries landed in Nigeria in 1822 (Ekwueme, 2001). With the coming of missionaries into this country, they established typical missionary schools. They first established primary school at Badagry where they trained the first generation of Teachers. With the establishment of schools come the need to train teachers who will carry out the task of imparting knowledge to the young ones. But the basic aims of missionary's school focused on winning souls for Christ. The missionaries were consciously or unconsciously the agent of oppressive and exploitative foreign presence There was no distinction between a school teacher and a catechist, for the teacher was basically an evangelist in addition to the teaching job.

Formal teacher education programmes begin in Nigeria in 1896 when St. Andrews College was established by the Church missionary society at Oyo to train People for the services of the CMS Yoruba mission (Abdul Malik, 2007). Some of those Institutions were meant to train teachers for the primary schools. It is important that we should examine the status of teaching during that time. The then teaching in Nigeria was in two fields, first at as an apprentice teacher and then on the job training. The missionaries provided the curriculum to be taught in the schools and also set up professional standard for the teacher and teacher education programmes. The syllabus consisted mainly of New Testament, preaching and theology, Hygiene, Geography, History, English, Carpentry and Mensory. The first category of teachers included primary school leavers who were sent into the classrooms on probationary basis. The teachers were under close supervision by European masters and Pastors. Those teachers were serving as auxiliary teachers. After teaching for a number of years were sent for the further training at teacher training schools. The teacher then entered into the second category. With the intervention of colonial government into the educational scene in 1882, more teacher training colleges were established in different parts of Nigeria. Some of the Institutions include: Baptist Training College Ogbomoso, (1897) St. Paul's Training Colleges, Akwa (1904). Oran Training Institute Ibadan, (1905). United Missionary College, Ibadan (1928) and St. Charles Training College Onitsha, (1929) as well as Teachers Training College Katsina (1929). The schools were meant for on-the-job training of teachers. The two-tier system of teacher training programme, recommended by Phelps-Stoke commission of 1911, was available for the education of teachers-the Elementary Teacher Certificate (TTC) or Grade III Certificate and High Elementary Teacher Certificate or Grade II (HETC). For the Grade III teacher's Certificate primary (standard six) certificate and years of experience (obtained from auxiliary service) were qualification for admission into Grade III Elementary Teacher Training Colleges. Having to teach for another two years or more after obtaining Grade III Certificate, would earn such candidate qualification to go for another two-year training for the Grade II High Elementary Teacher's Certificate. This system of teacher training continued in Nigeria for long time until 1950's. That was the state of teaching in Nigeria until the dawn of educational, economic and political realities of 1950's, 1960's and 1970's. During that period schools had rapidly increased both (public and private) as response to population explosion hence the need for more teachers. In an apparent response to that, the colonial government in 1959 set up the Ashby commission to look into the future needs of tertiary education in the country. As part of the recommendation of the

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commission, the federal government gave approval for the establishment of advanced teacher's training colleges in the country which later become colleges of education for the award of Nigerian Certificate of education (NCE).

The decades of 1960's and 1970's was turning points in the history of teaching in particular and education in general. There were the National Curriculum Conference and National Seminar on Policy of Education in 1969 and 1973 respectively which eventually led to the National Policy of Education in 1977. 1976, when the Universal Primary Education (UPE) scheme was launched. Teacher training schools were established to train teachers across the federation. The schools trained teachers (prospective) from nine months to two years, thus the influx of every body into teaching including the dropouts and dregs of educational system. This situation remains unchanged till today (Ekwueme, 2001). In 1939, a nine-month Teacher Training course in Agriculture was introduced at Ibadan and Umuahia. However, when Nigeria attained independence, the government opened Universities and Colleges of Education offering professional qualification, in teaching such as N.C.E, B.A. (Ed) B.Sc. (Ed) and B.Ed. respectively (Bamgbaiye, 2005).

Presently the following Institutions are responsible for the training of teachers:

1. Colleges of Education
2. Faculties of Education
3. Institute of Education
4. National Teachers Institute (NTI)
5. Schools of Education for Nigerian Languages (NINLAN)
6. National Mathematical Center (NMC)

Professionalization of Teaching at Secondary School Level of Education in Nigeria

Professionalization of teaching especially at secondary level of education in the country have been a point of discussion over the years Ekwueme (2001) posited that, the word profession is intimately related to the type of job/occupation from which an individual earns a living. According to him there is an outright ambiguity in the way many people use this word. This has made people to call themselves and to be called by others as professionals. It therefore, appeared pertinent to define the word profession. Some of the possible definitions of the word "profession" include the following:

1. An occupation or an employment (for which one has a calling) especially one that is possible only after advanced education and specialized training, and above all respected in the society, as honorable.
2. A calling in which one professed to have acquired special training used by either instructing, guiding or advising others or serving them in some Art
3. A kind of job that required its practitioner to possess a sound education and special training before he/she can be recognized as professionals.
4. A career in which all practitioners are guided by an effective code of conduct entry and exit measures. Examples of a profession are Teaching, Law, Medicine, Accountancy, Engineering etc.

Almost all occupations of the world have professional bodies that guide, regulate and direct their activities. The teaching profession at secondary level of education is not an exception. The teaching profession therefore has code of conduct and these are being enforced by the Teachers Registration Council of Nigeria (TRCN) and the Nigerian Union of Teachers (NUT) the enforcement, restriction and protection of the ethics of the teaching profession and the conduct are the sole responsibility of the employer. In this case, the Board or body of education has the right to execute and protect the provisions of the ethics of the teaching profession and its conduct. Workers can only be recognized based on their Union level of professional competence and the ability to stay by the body that binds or unites them together as a lawful professional body or professional Association. Nigerian teachers have the Nigerian Union of Teachers (NUT). Though it is a trade union, it equally helps to bring the Nigerian teachers together. However, at the moment it is still a teachers' union, which is restricted to Primary and Secondary Schools Teachers in Nigeria. (Mahuta, 2009)

Professionalizing teaching at Secondary School Level of Education in Nigeria

Major problems associated with professionalizing teaching especially at secondary school level of education in Nigeria in spite of the numerous problems facing the teaching profession and secondary school teachers in Nigeria, there are steps to be taken in order to better professionalize secondary school level of education teaching in Nigeria. Some of these steps or ways are as follows:

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1. The Teachers Registration Council of Nigeria (TRCN) should live up to the expectation by ensuring that only trained secondary schools' teachers who are qualified to be in the teaching profession, remain in it.
2. There should be a strong union especially at secondary school level of education to control the entire activities of the teaching profession such as entry, courses, code of ethics and certification.
3. The reward received includes that of prestige accorded to the profession as well as earnings, which are all symbols of the professional's achievement
4. There should be strictness in admission and certification of people into the profession.
5. Teachers without teaching qualification should be made to acquire such
6. The teaching profession should not admit or permit others who do not belongs to the profession to practice it so as to maintain the characteristics of control of entry.

There should be a special salary scale for the members of the teaching profession in Nigeria. Presently, teachers in Nigeria are seriously agitating for a special salary for teachers of Secondary Schools. The salary scale being agitated for by teachers is called 'Teachers Salary Scale (TSS). Doubtless, the teaching profession in Nigeria is suffering from societal misplacement and neglect. This attitude has made education to suffer and is resulting a decline in educational standards. Yet education remains a strong tool for the development of the society. There is therefore, the need for the TRCN to ensure the implementation of the Teachers Salary Scale (TSS), especially secondary school teachers in order to improve the remuneration given to teachers.

Problems of Professionalizing Teaching at Secondary School Level of Education in Nigeria

There are quite a number of problems bedeviling the professionalization of teaching especially at secondary school level of education in Nigeria. Some of these problems are as follows:

1. Unrealistic and wrong perception of the teaching profession held by the general public. Unfortunately, this is promoted by some members of the profession.
2. Functional disagreement among secondary school teachers about the purpose of education, and ignorance about contradictions across desired functions
3. The question of who is really in control of the standards, and policies encompassing secondary level of education and educational reforms in Nigeria.
4. The problems of occupational insecurity coupled with the lack of training and upgrading the general conduct of the ethics of the teaching profession especially at secondary school in the Country.
5. The teaching profession in Nigeria has suffered and is still suffering due to many factors, namely: i) Competence factors ii) Quality factors iii) Institutional factors iv) Economic factors and v) National factors

Ways of improving the status of teaching at Secondary School Level of Education in Nigeria

The following are some of the ways of improving the status of Teaching at secondary school level of education in Nigeria they are:

1. Secondary school teachers are not only restricted to providing knowledge and qualifications, but also universal ethical principles of social justice, tolerance and peace. They also play important role in the economic and cultural development of the society. Secondary school teachers share the concerns of parents and youths concerning the sociolect-economic development of Nigeria. However, teachers are facing pressures from the governments and employees who limit their performance by poor remuneration and therefore alter the nature of their responsibilities by imposing on them undue adjustment to the serious economic, social and cultural problems stemming from the current global and social challenges.
2. It is important to grant the teaching profession at secondary level of education a high status, not just for the sake of quality of education, but also for the progress of society as a whole. Society needs quality secondary school education and thus, highly qualified teachers, to ensure social and economic development.

Teacher Education at secondary school level of education in Nigeria

Teacher Education Programmes in Nigeria are the designed educational programmes, whose contents are meant to offer special training for intending teachers such as the pre-service and the in-service teachers. The global trend in Teacher Education seeks the improvement and systematic application of recent strategies, methods, innovations in education to meet up with the past developing and global challenges in society. The only possible means of equipping the individual is through the provision of skills, information and knowledge for advancement. Teacher Education Programmes provide valuable knowledge, information and skills for teacher-trainees. This is to equip them to be able to face the challenges of training others

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in the society states that a coherent teacher education programme should systematically embrace integrated curriculum innovation, which reflects the social, economic and political environment of the modern society, an educational innovation which seeks to succeed, must necessarily involve a reorientation of teachers' education to accept new challenges. (Oyekan, 2000)

Teacher education Programmes in Nigeria should enhance human quality; embrace innovations, bring about social changes and integrate individuals to the society with the knowledge acquired for problem solving. A functional programme is that which promotes efficiency and effective display of the knowledge and skills acquired by the teachers and teacher-trainees. However, potential teachers should be professionally rational, positively functional, and administratively competent. Therefore, they should be flexible and liberal in executing their duties. These qualities or attributes will allow a teacher to handle the teaching problems in the educational environment. It is in view of the importance attached to Teacher Education Programmes in Nigeria that the National Policy on Education (2014) states that, since no Education system can rise above the quality of its Teachers Teacher education shall continue to be given major emphasis in all Educational Planning and development. The minimum qualification for entry into the teaching profession shall be the Nigerian Certificate Of Education (NCE). The fact that, no education system may rise above the quality of its teachers, makes Teacher Education Programmes to occupy a vital portion in the planning and implementation of educational policies and programmes (Mahuta, 2009).

The Goals of Teacher Education at secondary level of education in Nigeria

The National Policy on Education (2013) outlines the goals of Teacher Education Programmes in Nigeria as follows:

1. to produce highly motivated, conscientious and efficient classroom teachers for all levels of our educational system
2. to encourage further, the spirit of enquiry and creativity in teachers
3. to help teachers to fit into social life of the community and society at large and enhance their commitment to national goals
4. to provide teachers with the intellectual and professional background adequate for their assignment and to make them and to make them adaptable to any changing situation not only in the life of their country, but in the wider world.

Qualities of Secondary School Teacher

Teaching profession has its own ethics, rules and so its professional teachers ought to have some basic qualities. An ideal teacher to do his job satisfactorily needs to possess the following:

1. Bright and cheerful disposition
2. Scholarship/expertise- without this one can never be a teacher i.e. must know his subject matter very well and can make others to understand the subject
3. Firmness and determination- always stick to institutional policy and feel detrimental to succeed in your task.
4. Paragon (Model) of virtues – always practice what you preach
5. A good command of language- an important asset for a teacher clarity, fluency- not too fast or too slow but moderate with clear voice, be modified of grammatical mistakes
6. Fair judgment and impartiality- in or outside the school treat all equally, especially in class discipline and performance assessment
7. Sincerity- be man of truth and frankness
8. Adaptability- needs to be daily aspire, expand knowledge, ability to respond intelligently to new similar problems to promote own states
9. Punctuality and time consciousness- be practiced as much as possible
10. Satisfactory inter-staff relationship has a good relationship with other teaching and non-teaching staff for the job satisfaction
11. Sociability out the school- good understanding between the school and immediate community.

The Nature of Teaching at Secondary School level of Education

Three focal points in Education: Teacher, Child and subject. Teaching is the relationship which we established between these three. Conclusively the role of a teacher in transforming Nigeria ought to reflect the following:

1. Guides and counsels, the masses professionally
2. Onward looking for a better capacity building and education unreluctantly
3. Obedient and loyal to the constituted authority to serve as a model
4. Demonstrates discipline and orderliness both in words and in action
5. Teaches and trains to build a better future generation

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6. Earnestly erases illiteracy and ignorance steadily and systematically
7. Appear to be an agent of civilization and academic excellence
8. Curves inefficiently and serve as a Centre of excellence at all level of Education
9. Heads towards honesty, hard work, commitment and sacrifice to duty
10. Endeavors to promote expertise at all spheres of knowledge
11. Rear his clients well to help remove away the darkness of life from the society
(Hakimi, 2007)

Conclusion

It could be concluded that, a teacher has a tremendous role to play in the realization of the National objectives based on the National policy on Education via Millennium Development Goals. To provide this important instrument for the socio-economic and National development of the Giant of Africa which in turn will lead to the transformation of Nigeria emphasis should be given on teacher and teaching pupil and the immediate community, improvement of learning environment, development of appropriate instructional materials and their usage, effective and efficient school management and multi-optional Teacher Education Programmes. If these are given adequate attention in the provision of education in Nigeria, it would actualize the nation's agenda in producing elites that would man different sectors of the nation's economy.

Recommendations

1. Adequate funding of the secondary school level of education should be given priority in line with UNESCO minimum requirement of 26% of the Total budget of a given country to be allocated to Education.
2. Training and Re-training of secondary school teachers via in-service and on the job training which include among others, attending Conferences both Local and International, Workshops, Seminars and other Refresher Courses for capacity building should be facilitated by educational managers.
3. New Proposed Teacher's Salary Scale (TSS) and other incentives should be re-visited and implemented as this will in turn boost secondary school teacher's Morale to put more inputs for the realization of secondary school Educational goals and objectives for National development.
4. Re-visiting the previous Professional Teacher Development Programme 2013 Cluster Training Centers from December 2013 to March 2014 in the 23 Local Governments of Sokoto State organized by the Faculty of Education and Extension Services, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto in Collaboration with UBE Sokoto State to be approved as Permanent and NCE awarding Centers based on contact Sessions.
5. TETFund intervention on Staff Development should consider incorporating Secondary Schools Teachers Training as a priority for the realization of the nations' vision to be a reality.

Acknowledgement

We wish to extend my gratitude to the Almighty Allah for sparing our lives to make my contributions in the Zamfara International Journal of Education (ZIJE). We also wish to extend our sincere appreciation and gratitude to our Mentors and other Colleagues in the Department of Educational Foundations Faculty of Education and Extension Services (UDUS) for their numerous contributions to my academic achievement.

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